

Sustainability in Fish Farming: A Bibliometric Mapping of the Global Literature

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Fish farming has emerged as an integral component of the global food system and has made a substantial contribution to food security and socio-economic development. However, with the growing concerns of environmental management and the efficient use of resources, the importance of fish farming as a sustainable practice has been emphasised more and more by researchers. The present study offers an extensive bibliometric analysis of fish farming and sustainability research from all over the world and seeks to contribute to the identification of trends, prominent researchers, and journals, as well as emerging research areas. For the present study, out of the 284 data points from the Web of Science, only 222 have been used. The time period considered for the present study ranges from 1994 to 2025. The bibliometric analysis has been made easier with the help of Biblioshiny, which focuses on the major areas of the research, such as author information, publications per year, the most relevant sources, production of the source, the most important authors, the most prominent countries, the trending topics, and the word cloud.

Keywords: Fish farming, sustainability, aquaculture, bibliometric analysis, environmental management

Fish farming, also called aquaculture, has developed as one of the most dynamic food production sectors in the world and has become a vital sector in meeting the food and nutritional needs of the increasing global population, food security, and rural livelihoods (Garlock et al., 2024). With the increasing tendency of capture fisheries to meet or exceed their sustainability limits, fish farming has been increasingly encouraged as a viable option to meet the demand for fish and fish products. However, the increasing dynamics of fish farming have also led to several concerns about the environmental, resource efficiency, equity, and economic sustainability issues (Jiang et al., 2022). These challenges have put the concept of sustainability at the forefront of research, policy, and practices in aquaculture (Jiang et al., 2022). There are several dimensions of sustainability in fish farming, including environmental factors such as water quality, biodiversity, feed availability, and waste management (Tacon & Metian, 2015). There are also economic factors such as productivity, profitability, and market access, as well as social factors such as employment, food safety, and community well-being. All these factors are crucial in the sustainability of fish farming (Boyd et al., 2022).

In recent decades, a significant amount of scientific literature has

focused on these interconnected dimensions, introducing technological innovations, management practices, governance frameworks, and policy interventions that promote sustainable aquaculture development. As a result, research on sustainability in fish farming has expanded across various disciplines, regions, and methodological approaches. The existing literature, despite a surge in publications, remains fragmented, complicating the identification of key research themes, influential authors, collaboration patterns, and emerging areas. Traditional narrative reviews often fail to systematically capture extensive bibliographic data and visualise research evolution. Bibliometric research offers a strong tool for quantitatively evaluating the scientific landscape, exploring knowledge structures, and identifying trends in scientific research production. This study aims to conduct comprehensive bibliometric research on the global literature related to sustainability in fish farming. By exploring publication patterns, citation patterns, and prominent research articles, authors, and institutions, as well as research clusters, this study aims to offer a comprehensive picture of how sustainability has been studied and researched in the context of fish farming as a scientific discipline. The research results are expected to be useful for future research, offering insights into research gaps and new research areas, and contributing to future research in the context of more sustainable aquaculture production.

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Review of Literature

A thematic review is employed in this study to effectively organise and synthesise the existing literature on the chosen theme by identifying recurring patterns, major themes, and significant areas of research in the chosen theme. In this study, two themes have been identified: one is fish farming, and the other is sustainability.

Fish Farming

Fish farming, an essential aspect of aquaculture, has become increasingly important worldwide as it helps to supplement declining capture fisheries and meet the rising demand for animal protein. Research shows that fish farming is a rapidly growing industry that contributes to food security, generates employment,

and promotes rural development (FAO, 2022). Improvements in breeding, feed formulation, and farm management have greatly enhanced productivity and survival rates in freshwater, brackish, and marine farming systems (Cao et al., 2021). Fish farming in the district is still in its early stages, but it holds immense potential for enhancing economic prosperity, improving living standards, ensuring food security, providing better sanitation facilities, creating employment opportunities, and offering alternative livelihood options. Moreover, value-added programs related to fish products are still underutilised, and this is a good opportunity for future growth (Aswathy & G, 2021). Fish farming faces several challenges related to finance, technology, ecology, production, business, and market (Phukan & Barman, 2016). The major challenges faced by the fish farmers for the production and marketing of inland fish include high mortality of fish, lack of quality fish seed, lack of financial support, perishability of the product, competition, and lack of storage facilities. Providing training to fish farmers will help them increase their returns from fish farming and will encourage them to invest more in the industry. Moreover, providing scientific storage solutions to marketing intermediaries will help them handle larger quantities of the product, and ultimately, the production of fish will increase (Ashok, 2022). Technologies such as recirculating aquaculture systems, automated feeding systems, water quality sensors, and computerised fish farm management systems have also been explored for the purpose. Such innovations indicate an emerging trend in fish farm research, which is moving away from the traditional production-oriented approach (Goddek et al., 2018).

Sustainability

Sustainability has emerged as an important area of focus in aquaculture research, which underlines the significance of ensuring the sustainability of fish farming systems. Sustainable fish farming is usually considered through the lens of the triple bottom line, which considers environmental sustainability, economic viability, and social equity. (Barton et al., 2023). Environmental sustainability is an important area of focus for fish farming research. Various researchers have highlighted the negative impacts of fish farming on the environment, which include nutrient enrichment, degradation of sediments, pollution, and biodiversity loss (Hassan, 2025). Excess feed and fish waste are also major causes of eutrophication, leading to oxygen depletion and the deterioration of the surrounding aquatic ecosystems (Troell et al., 2009). Recirculating Aquaculture Systems (RAS) have been extensively researched due to their potential in conserving water, managing waste, and providing biosecurity benefits (Troell et al., 2009). Biofloc technology is increasingly being recognised as a viable and environmentally friendly method of aquaculture, which improves water quality and reduces feed costs (Crab et al., 2012). The ecological and economic risks associated with our dependence on traditional feed sources need to be carefully weighed. Alternative feed ingredients, including plant proteins, insects, algae, and microorganisms, need to be explored. Nutritional adequacy, growth rate, and environmental impact need to be balanced so that sustainable feed development can be seen as a key component of sustainability in the long run (Øverland et al., 2023). Regulations, certification, and best management practices are recognised as critical elements in reducing environmental impacts and promoting sustainable production. Sustainability has been highlighted in international guidelines and national aquaculture policies, but enforcement gaps exist, particularly in developing countries (Bush, 2019).

The evolution of themes in the literature indicates a shift from

impact-related research to solution and integration-related research. The increasing number of publications, the literature is still fragmented, covering many disciplines and regions of the globe. This indicates the need for bibliometric mapping to identify major themes, research fronts, and gaps in sustainability-oriented research in fish farming.

Method

Bibliometric analysis was employed to examine the literature from the Web of Science. There are 284 datasets available, but only 222 were utilised in this study. Biblioshiny was used to import data for analysis and to create various visualisations. While Biblioshiny offers many options, we focused on specific areas such as the main information about authors, publications per year, the most relevant sources, production of sources over time, the most influential authors, citation trends by country, trending topics, and a word cloud. In this study, publication years between 1994 to 2025 were selected. Web of Science was used to select research articles focusing on various categories, including fisheries, environmental sciences, marine and freshwater biology, green sustainable science and technology, environmental studies, food science and technology, water resources, environmental engineering, multidisciplinary sciences, agricultural economics, and policy economics. All articles were published in English.

Figure 1

Flow Chart of Bibliometric Analysis

Note. Source: Author owns

Results and Discussion

Overview of Literature on Fish Farming and Sustainability

The results of the bibliometric study, covering the period from 1994 to 2025, indicate that this research field is expanding continuously. The number of documents published is 222, and they are drawn from 91 sources. The annual growth rate is 12.25%, and the collaboration level is high, as indicated by the number of contributing authors, which is 1,115, and the number of co-authors, who are on average 5.43 per document. Garlock et al. (2024) states that sustainable aquaculture is gaining more and more importance in meeting global food security and environmental issues. The co-authorship of international authors is also impressive, at 38.74%. The research

field is also diverse, as indicated by the number of author keywords, which is 817, and it is also well-supported with references, as indicated by the total number of citations, which is 13,465. The age of documents is also relatively recent, at 6.74 years, and the number of citations per document is also impressive, at 25.68 on average.

Figure 2

Overview of Literature on Fish Farming and Sustainability

Publication Per Year

The trend of annual publications shows a slow and irregular growth pattern in the initial years (1994-2005), followed by a gradual rise from 2006 onwards. There has been a significant acceleration in the rate of publications from around 2016, with a steep rise in publications from after 2020, peaking in recent years. This shows a rise in interest in research within this field, especially in the last ten years, owing to its increased scientific and practical relevance.

Figure 3

Publication Per Year

Figure 4

Most Relevant Sources

Most Relevant Sources

From the results of the most relevant source analysis, the leading journal is "Aquaculture," which published the highest number of documents, reaching 35. The second leading journal is "Sustainability," which published 17 documents. Other important journals that published documents include "Aquaculture Research" and the "Journal of Cleaner Production," each publishing 9 documents. Additionally, other important journals include "Aquaculture International" and "Reviews in Aquaculture," each publishing 8 documents. Therefore, the trend shows that while there

is specialisation in the key journals, other journals are also available. Moreover, the trend shows an increase in the number of interdisciplinary journals related to sustainability and environmental management.

Sources Production Over Time

The trends in the publications indicate that Aquaculture has always been the leading journal with a sharp increase in publications, especially after 2018. This is an indication of the journal's importance as the primary outlet for research in the field. Other leading journals, such as Aquaculture Research, Journal of Cleaner Production, Reviews in Aquaculture, and Aquaculture International, have shown steady growth, albeit at a relatively lower rate, with an increase in the rate of growth in the more recent period. This suggests the consolidation of the leading journals in the field of aquaculture, as well as the steady improvement in the sustainability-focused journals and the review journals in the research domain.

Figure 5

Sources Production over Time

Most Relevant Authors

From the analysis of the author's productivity, it is evident that none of the authors have made significant contributions to the domain. Owatari MS and Sánchez-Jerez P have the maximum number of publications, which is six. However, another author, Magnotti C, has published four papers. Moreover, other authors have published three papers each, which indicates that the author's structure is decentralised.

Figure 6

Most Relevant Authors

Most Cited Countries

From the country-wise citation analysis, China is at the top with 854 citations, followed by the United States with 562 citations. This indicates the impact of these two countries on the field. Even the European countries have shown good results in terms of the number of citations, with Italy having 392 citations, the United Kingdom having 359, and Sweden having 302. At the same time, the presence of emerging and developing countries such as Brazil, Egypt, and Zambia also indicates the global impact of the research.

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